
USE OF INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING A CULTURE OF PEACE**Mrs. Ketki G Satpute***Assistant Professor, Sree Narayana Guru College of Education*

And

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The General Assembly of the United Nations defines Culture of Peace as “All the values, attitudes and forms of behaviours that reflect respect for life, for human dignity and for all human rights, the rejection of violence in all its forms and commitment to the principles of freedom, justice, solidarity, tolerance and understanding between people.” In order to be there a culture of peace, the world must learn to live together peacefully. In the process of weaving a culture of peace the role of education is vital. Initiating a peaceful culture should start from the teacher itself, because the role of teacher is very crucial in inculcating values, attitudes, behaviours, habits among the children. The teachers must bring change in themselves first, to be the peace-builders.

Hence the present study used the Quasi-Experimental pre-test-post-test non-equivalent group design to develop culture of peace among student-teachers. The modules of innovative strategies were designed by the researcher and implemented on Experimental group. The inferential analysis used t-test, paired t-test and ANCOVA. The results show that innovative strategies were useful in developing culture of peace among student-teachers.

INTRODUCTION

The General Assembly of the United Nations that proclaimed the years 2001-2010 the International decade for a Culture of Peace and Non-violence for the children of the world, defines a Culture of Peace as “All the values, attitudes and forms of behaviours that reflect respect for life, for human dignity and for all human rights, the rejection of violence in all its forms and commitment to the principles of freedom, justice, solidarity, tolerance and understanding between people.”

In order to be there a culture of peace, the world must learn to live together peacefully. In the process of weaving a culture of peace the role of education is vital. Initiating a peaceful culture should start from the teacher itself, because the role of teacher is very crucial in inculcating values, attitudes, behaviours, habits among the children, required for solving the problems unimaginable today. Teachers are role models for us. They need to be more compassionate, caring and tolerant. Children will learn peace values only if they are modelled by their teachers and elders. Hence, they must bring change in themselves first, to be the peace-builders. They must develop the attitudes and behaviours of appreciation, co-operation, belongingness, trust and spirit of learning. Hence it is necessary to equip the ‘would be’ teachers with necessary skills, attitudes and values conducive to peace behaviour and prepare them to make conscious efforts and contribute towards creating a culture of peace.

NEED AND RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

As lamented by Mondal (2014), 'a strong need is being felt by educationists, philosophers, scientists and political leaders to rejuvenate the human values, which may bring long lasting peace on this planet'. Peace is a prime requirement for progress and national integration. Peace begins with the individual and spreads to the family, to the community, to the nation, and to the global village. Promoting a culture of peace, hence, is essential. The world has changed in leaps and bound over the centuries. With this world torn with conflicts and violence, the need for peace building and peace making cannot be over emphasized. Responding to this need, the National Curriculum Framework (2005) by NCERT has underlined that education must develop sensitivity in individuals to their social environment. The qualities essential for peace building should be nurtured among students. The action for nurturing and peace building must be located in the educational system. The purpose of education goes beyond the propagation of knowledge. The Delor's report (1996) on learning to live together as the central pillar of education proposes that education must be geared to promote a culture of peace, tolerance, democratic values, human rights and duties among students. Lasting peace may depend on educating future generations into the competencies, perspectives, attitudes, values, and behavioural patterns that will enable them to build and maintain peace. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to investigate and understand how different techniques and strategies can be more widely adapted and effectively use in order to equip the student-teachers with attitudes and wide range of skills that help them cope effectively with the challenges of everyday life, thereby giving them an edge for creating more beautiful and peaceful world.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

After reviewing the related literature, the researcher realized that Peace Research is relatively young and new area of research. Hence, majority of the initial work consists of conceptual papers, research articles and books, focused mainly on understanding the holistic concept of peace. The major contributors in this area are Galtung (1969,1981), Takeshi Ishida (1969), Wiberg (1981), Reardon Betty (1988), (Fountain 1999), (Harris 2004), (Danesh 2006) to name a few. Peace Education Programs and curriculums were developed in many countries, gradually, such as Dream of Good, Swedish Project (Henning, 2004), Peace in the eyes of Israeli and Palestinians (Solomon 2006), Peace Education Program beyond ethnocentrism and violence (Kester 2008), Youth Peace Initiative Model, Sydney Project (Susy 2010), REPLICAPEP by Najjuma (2011) to name a few. Majority of these programmes were school-based and were developed for post-conflict societies. The researcher observed that lot of work has been done on global level in this field during the last five decades all over the world. Comparatively, the work has started recently in India. She observed that, the need for peace, peace education and the importance of education as the means to incorporate peace feelings at all levels of life, is echoed in most of the articles and papers published in India in the peace research area. Such as Rajput (2011), Rani (2015), Pundeer (2012), Upadhyay (2009), Udaykumar (2009), Mondal (2014). The researcher came across with few surveys that have been conducted in India. Survey to find out the attitude towards Peace Education, Deca (2011), Dhingra (2015), to identify strategies for integrating Peace education in schools (Mishra, 2013).

Few experimental and mixed method studies used various approaches and strategies for promoting peace in all the spheres of life. Borkar (2009) used stories as method of teaching with focus on core human values. Chitkamba (2011) adapted process curriculum approach and developed moral education programme to facilitate peaceful conflict negotiations. Suramya (2013) tried to find out the effectiveness of Yoga in internalization of peace behaviour. Bhatia (2013) used drawings for finding out the perceptions of students towards peace and based on it designed a peace curriculum to develop peace efficacy among students. Majority of these studies were school-based. Teacher Education area not much explored. Also, keeping in mind the need of hour that teachers need to be peace-builders, the researcher decided to experiment with innovative strategies for developing a culture of peace among student teachers.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“Use of Innovative Strategies for Developing a Culture of Peace”.

VARIABLES OF RESEARCH

A. Independent variable : Innovative Strategies

B. Dependent variable : Culture of Peace

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

Innovative Strategies: For the present study, Innovative Strategies are those which the researcher would be using in the classroom for developing culture of peace among student teachers, which includes:

1. Sharing Game 2. Film clippings 3. Art and Drama 4. Meditation 5. Auto-suggestions

Culture of Peace: In the present study it consists of values, attitudes and skills developed among student teachers through Innovative Strategies.

AIM OF THE STUDY

To study the use of Innovative Strategies for developing a Culture of Peace.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study and compare the pre-test scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace.
2. To study and compare the post test scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace.
3. To compare the pre-test and post-test scores of control group of development of culture of peace.
4. To compare the pre-test and post-test scores of experimental group of development of culture of peace.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY:

1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace.
2. There is no significant difference in the post test scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace.
3. There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of control group of development of culture of peace.

4. There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of experimental group of development of culture of peace.

SCOPE AND DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study includes only 2nd year student-teachers of two B.Ed. colleges affiliated to Mumbai University located in Navi Mumbai. In the present study Culture of Peace consists of values, attitudes and skills developed through the use of innovative strategies. It explores the usefulness of only those strategies designed and implemented by the researcher. The sample size is small as per the population hence the extent to which the findings can be generalised is limited.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The present study aimed at using the innovative strategies for developing a culture of peace among student-teachers of B.Ed. colleges, hence the method adopted was Experimental Method. The researcher has used intact classes of B.Ed., hence Quasi Experimental method of pre-test post-test non-equivalent group design was adapted.

The Pre-test Post-test Non-Equivalent Group Design is described symbolically as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} O_1 & X & O_2 \\ O_3 & C & O_4 \end{array}$$

Where,

O_1 and O_3 = Pre-test Scores and O_2 and O_4 = Post-test Scores

And, X: Experimental Group & C: Control Group

Five modules of Innovative strategies namely, 1. Sharing Game 2. Film Clippings 3. Art and Drama 4. Meditation 5. Auto-suggestions, were planned, prepared and used on experimental group. Before intervention program pre-test was administered to both control group and experimental group. The control group was not given any treatment. At the end of the programme post-test was administered to the students of both the control group and experimental group. Scores were analysed using statistical techniques.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUE OF THE STUDY

In the present study, for experimentation the researcher included student teachers studying in B.Ed. Colleges affiliated to Mumbai University. Purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of two B.Ed. colleges from the same geographical area i.e. Navi Mumbai. They were assigned randomly, one as Experimental Group and the other as Control Group. The total sample size was 80 students, 40 students in the Control group and 40 students in Experimental group.

TOOLS OF THE RESEARCH

The following tools were employed for the collection of the necessary data.

1. A Five-point Likert Scale was developed by the researcher for measuring development of culture of peace. The final form of the tool has 61 items constructed with 3 dimensions i.e. values, attitudes and skills. The Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was found to be 0.89.

2. Observation schedule was prepared by the researcher to observe the behaviour of the student teachers while innovative strategies were used during intervention programme.

INTERVENTION PROGRAMME

The Modules of Innovative Strategies developed by the researcher were implemented on Experimental group. The content of the modules developed revolved around fostering attitude, values and skills for development of culture of peace among student teachers. The modules designed were participatory, student-driven and activity base. The brief description of each module is as follows:

1. Sharing Game: Emphasis was given on sharing learner's own experiences in the class, reflect on it, discuss and create new peace stories among these experiences.
2. Film-clippings: Five short film-clippings on various subjects like love, empathy, co-operation, positive thinking, understanding, ecological concerns etc. were shown. After each screening of the film, critical discussion and reflection was conducted.
3. Art and Drama: Two different activities were conducted under this; Improvisation and Dance. In improvisation students were asked to imagine their destination of peace and to go on this journey along-with their peers. They were asked to present the skit on it in the class. In a second activity they were asked to choreograph and perform on a selected audio song with a theme on gender discrimination, equality, humanity, love.
4. Meditation: Few simple meditation techniques were demonstrated which were practised regularly by the students during intervention programme.
5. Auto-suggestion: A work-shop on self-awareness was conducted, which included different games on self-knowledge, problem-solving, critical thinking etc. They were asked to frame positive statements (auto-suggestion) about oneself, life and follow them regularly.

TECHNIQUES OF DATA ANALYSIS

The researcher used Descriptive Statistical Techniques such as Measures of central tendency: Mean, Median and Mode, Measures of Variability: Standard Deviation and Graphical representation. For Inferential statistical technique 't' test, paired t-test and ANCOVA was used.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace.

Table 1.1

Difference in the pre-test scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace.

Pre-test	N	Mean	SD	df	t-ratio	P	Significance at 0.01 Level
Control Group	40	240.15	13.34	78	2.51	0.014	Not Significant
Experimental Group	40	248.99	17.60				

For above Table, for $N=80$, $df=78$, tabulated $t=1.99$ at 0.05 level and $t=2.64$ at 0.01 For the above hypothesis, it is observed that t -ratio is not significant. That means hypothesis is accepted at 0.01 level. But, it shows significant difference at 0.05 level. That means null hypothesis is accepted only at 0.01 level. It may be concluded that there is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the post test scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace.

On testing of null hypothesis 1, it was found that the control group and experimental group do not differ significantly on total pre-test score of culture of peace at 0.01 level, but at 0.05 level it shows significant difference. The mean of experimental group is higher than that of the control group. Since at pre-test level initial differences are seen in control group and experimental group, **Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) has been performed to find the true effect of intervention after adjusting for pre-test scores.** Post-assessment scores are analysed using ANCOVA, in which the effect of pre-test has been partialled out from the post-test scores on each of the dependent variable and pre-assessment scores are used as co-variant.

Table 2.1 shows the adjusted post-test mean scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace after partialling out the effect of pre-test scores

Table 2.1

Adjusted post-test mean scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace

Groups	Observed Mean	Adjusted Mean
Control Group	240.75	243.37
Experimental Group	257.40	254.78

From the above table 2.1, it can be seen that the post-test means for control group (240.75) is adjusted upward by ANCOVA (243.37), whereas the post-test mean for experimental group (257.40) is adjusted downward (254.78). ANCOVA determines whether these post-test means differ significantly from each other.

Table 2.2 shows the relevant statistics of ANCOVA for post-test mean scores of culture of peace of control group and experimental group.

Table 2.2

Relevant Statistics of ANCOVA for post-test mean scores of culture of peace of control group and experimental group.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Contrast	2410.713	1	2410.713	20.897	.000
Error	8882.715	77	115.360		

For $N=80$, $df(1,77)$, tabulated $F=3.96$ at 0.05 level and $F=6.96$ at 0.01 level.

It can be seen from Table 2.2 that the obtained F ratio (20.89) is significant at 0.01 level, hence significant difference is found between the two samples, which rejects the null hypothesis. Thus, it can be stated that there is significant difference in the post test mean scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace.

Null Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of control group of development of culture of peace.

Table 3.1

Differences in the pre-test and post-test scores of control group of development of culture of peace.

Control Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-ratio	P	Significance at 0.01 level
Pre-test	40	240.15	13.34	39	0.359	0.7214	Not significant
Post-Test	40	240.75	12.53				

For above Table, for $N=40$, $df=39$, tabulated $t=2.02$ at 0.05 level and $t=2.71$ at 0.01

For the above hypothesis, obtained 't' value 0.359 is less than table value 't' (2.71) at 0.01 level of significance, 'p' value is greater than 0.05, hence it is not significant. The null hypothesis is therefore accepted. And therefore, there is no significant difference in the pre-test and post test scores of control group of the development of culture of peace.

Null Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of experimental group of development of culture of peace.

Table 4.1

Differences in the pre-test and post test scores of experimental group of development of culture of peace

Experimental Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-ratio	P	Significance at 0.001 level
Pre-test	40	248.99	17.60	39	3.85	0.0004	Significant
Post-Test	40	257.40	15.68				

For above Table, for $N=40$, $df=39$, tabulated $t=2.02$ at 0.05 level and $t=2.71$ at 0.01

For the above hypothesis, the 't' ratio obtained for differences in the pre-test and post-test scores of experimental group for development of culture of peace is 3.85, which is significant at 0.01 level. Therefore, null hypothesis is rejected. There is significant difference in the pre-test and post test scores of experimental group of development of culture of peace.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis 1: No significant difference was found in the pre-test scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace. It shows that both groups are at the same

level of understanding at pre-test stage. It could be because they are from the same geographical area, they are exposed to same syllabus of 2-year B.Ed. Course and their maturity level is almost equal.

Hypothesis 2

There is significant difference in the post test scores of control group and experimental group of development of culture of peace. The probable reason for this could be the intervention programme implemented by the researcher. This implies that the innovative strategies used by the researcher were effective in developing attitude, values and skills among student-teachers. It included five innovative strategies, each one of them participatory in the nature. It gave ample opportunity to each participant to actively participate in every activity. It helped improving their confidence. Each activity helped them to relate it with their own personal experiences, share it with the group, reflect on it and express their views/ opinions on it. It gave them food for thought. While creating stories of peace many of the students were emotionally involved into it. They cried at a time. But they came up with positive solutions to the problems faced by them. Kester (2007) who used storytelling experience as pedagogy for cultivating a culture of peace found it effective and concludes in his study that storytelling is a means to remember, share and create possibilities. Meditation exercises actually helped them to relax and they learned how to be calm and cool in midst of hectic life-styles, which is the need of the hour. Suramya (2013) who used Yoga as an instructional strategy also found that students experienced several physiological and psychological benefits from the practice of Yoga, which supports the findings of the present study. The activities conducted created free and open environment which is very essential for making learning joyful. Though significant difference was seen at pre-test stage, after partialling out the initial difference through ANCOVA, the significant difference at post-test stage, truly attributes to the intervention program carried out by the researcher.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of control group of development of culture of peace. The basic reason behind this could be non-exposure of control group to intervention programme. The control group was not given any treatment. Hence the post-test responses of the subjects were almost same as pre-test level. There was not much difference in the mean of the pre-test and post-test scores of control group.

Hypothesis 4

There is significant difference in the post test scores of experimental group of development of culture of peace. This shows that the use of innovative strategies had significant impact on the experimental group after implementing the strategies. The participants were exposed to strategies in innovative way. It made use of their personal experiences for sharing with each other and created new stories of peace. The meditations techniques they learned and practised during intervention program were easy and simple, which many of them started following on daily basis, as observed by the researcher. The activities were planned in such a way that, they participated and worked together. It encouraged them to communicate with each other and help solve their own problems,

express creatively and improved on their self-knowledge. Their involvement in the activities showed positive impact on their attitude. This could be the probable reason for developing values, skills and attitude conducive to peace due to which their post-test responses were improved compared to pre-test level. Many studies, such as Lesley (2011), Bhatnagar (2010), Borkar (2009), Caterall (2007), Malm & Lofgren (2007) supports the findings of the present study, that intervention programme had significant impact on experimental group.

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

Creating culture of peace requires a fundamental change in knowledge, attitudes, behaviour which enables the learners to take action for more peaceful world. In order to bring change at a larger level it should start from us. The present research is a small step towards this. Findings of the study reveal that participatory activities have brought action in the class as well as promoted preferred values for peace. The teachers can effectively implement these practically in their day to day life, can become the peace teachers and help bloom schools as nurseries of peace. They can become the peace-builders of the nation and can help to create the more peaceful and beautiful world.

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